

FLOOD DISASTER MANAGEMENT IN ASSAM

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ABSTRACT

In Assam the flood is a natural disaster and it's occurring due to the excessive rainfall and the people were affected by every year. In Assam economy the mainly dependent in agriculture sector in rural areas. The flood affects people every year due to the heavy monsoon and the various human man-made activities like deforestation. The other reason of flood in Assam is the Brahmaputra and Barak River during the heavy rainfall the river is flooded and it's affected the society of the people. In every year the flood is occur in Assam and thousands people are homeless and the biodiversity zone also affected, due to the worst flood the agricultural crops were damaged, infrastructure, Properties and including the communication system. The Assam state Disaster Management authority were also take various initiative steps to control the flood and erosion in Assam. To control the flood situation in Assam we needed modern technology and the government implementation schemes. However, this research paper analysis the causes of Assam flood, socio-economic impact and the management system of Assam flood.

Keywords : Assam, Disaster Management, Disaster, Flood, Government.

Introduction

Disaster management is to conserve the lives of people and their property during the natural disaster or man-made disaster. In the vulnerable areas the Disasters are seen as the cause of hazards. In the low vulnerability area the hazards are occur and don't shown the result of disaster, the disaster is affecting the life of people and great damage agricultural land and property are the result shown of disaster. The disaster is affecting immeasurable damage with the varies geographical location.

The disaster had the following effects in concerned areas: In the normal day to day life is completely worried, the emergency systems are harmfully Persuade, the disaster is depending on the severity and intensity of the normal needs and processes are badly deteriorated and affected. In the vulnerable area disaster are the cause of hazard. In the low vulnerability area the hazard are occur but don't shown the result of disaster. Disaster management study is important because it helps us in the

process of resources management of disaster and to dealing with all the emergencies of humanitarian aspects. The Natural disaster activities had order to increased the awareness of disaster of response, preparedness and recovery during the disaster in all the vulnerable areas of hazard.

The research paper we will discuss the disaster management of flood in Assam. The flood is a natural disaster and it's occurring due to heavy rainfall and the geo-climatic conditions during monsoon season in Assam. In the Brahmaputra River the flood is occur every year in the state of Assam and the worst flood occur in august 2000 in the Brahmaputra valley. The flood cause because due to land erosion, human activities, disruption of roads and rail, and geomorphological changes and affecting the cultivated lands because of flood. After 1998 the biggest flood reported was in the year 2012 were 21 district was affected out of 27. The floods of Assam in 2013 occur due to heavy rainfall and affected 396 villages

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in 12 district and the agriculture land was destroyed almost 7000 hectares. The Assam flood 2014, the people of Assam were almost affected 42 lakh people and 85 people died during the flood in Assam. Recently in 2020 the flood is occur in Assam during the COVID-19 pandemic. In Assam the flood were initially started recently on May 2020 due to the heavy rainfall till July and its affected 2 to 3 million in 27 districts. According to Assam State disaster management authority we can see that more than 3000 villages were affected and 44 thousand people were moved in relief camps and agricultural land also destroyed. During the floods the animals were moved to another place because more than half of the area kaziranga national park and Pobitora wildlife sanctuary were affected. In 2020 the flood is caused due to the excess summer season and affected the state of Assam. Till July according to the meteorological department of Assam they receive rainfall almost 1,164 mm as compared to normal rainfall 894mm during the period. The Assam face major floods during post-independence period in 1954, 1962, 1972, 1977, 1984, 1998,2002, 2004 and 2012. Another major reason in Assam the flood is occur due to the bank of Erosion in Brahmaputra and Barak valley by their tributaries.

Study Area

The study area was we covered the area of Assam flood. The Assam is a state in northeastern India. The Assam state comprises in the Barak and Brahmaputra valley and is located 90 degree to 96 degree latitude in

north longitude 24 degree to 28 degree in East longitude. In Assam two rivers are Brahmaputra and Barak and it's the main source for agriculture and the water transportation in these regions. But during the monsoon season these two rivers were create natural disaster of flood due to heavy rainfall. In the state of Assam there is a Brahmaputra river and the river is so vast and carries a large quantity of water during the heavy rainfall and the floods occur. In Assam, Brahmaputra valley from Dhubri to kobo is joined in north bank with 20 tributaries and in south bank with 13 tributaries. The tributaries major north bank are Jia Barali and Subansiri were flow in Arunachal Pradesh, Pagladiya and manas were flow in from Bhutan. The Burhi are main south bank tributaries and Dhansiri from Nagaland, the Dihing from Arunachal Pradesh and kapili from Assam's Karbi angling district. Assam valley is hostages with agricultural land and habitat almost 27 million people. The state of Assam net cultivated area is 28,110 km² and the total agricultural land available for cultivation is 88 percent as per survey of economic 2017-18 [4] and 99% of the total area is rural.

According to the census of 2011 the state of Assam mostly 50% total population are dependent in agriculture sector for the economy. The study area covers 78396.28 km² of Assam and where the Brahmaputra River has its wide long of flood plains all through the state. Before entering the river in Bangladesh at a Golabari near Dubri trans-boundary river Brahmaputra enters Assam near kemi south of pashighat and runs 670 km.

Figure: Flood Hazard map of Assam

Methodology

In this research paper is a based on various secondary sources and the data were collected through various journal paper, newspaper, reports, internet and the various report writer were collected. However, the secondary sources data were collected through the Assam Disaster Management Authority and department of water resource of Assam.

Flood Management System of Assam

In 1954 after the disaster of flood in the country the government of India had announced the national policy of floods: the immediate, short-term and long-term measures. When national water policy had announced the flood control activities had started in Assam. The flood control In Assam there are various plan were prepared for the main areas where we need immediate and urgent attention were identified. In Assam the water resources department were take works primarily for the general development in the rural sector to protect the major townships for the both Brahmaputra valley and Barak Valley. In the important areas and the cities the scheme were had been taken for the drainage congestion.

1. Flood zoning area in Assam
2. Drainage improvement.
3. Construction of Embankments and flood walls.
4. Flood warning and forecasting.
5. Town protection works and anti-erosion
6. River training and bank protection works.

In Assam, according to the State water Resources Department the long term measures had not implemented yet for the flood and erosion problems of the state. Till now in Assam only short term and immediate measures are implemented for the flood.

Flood Management

According to the administration of district, the Water Commission of central is responsibility to controlled all the rivers in Assam. The central Water commission were discuss the warning to the Assam Disaster Management and District Disaster Management Authority for further spreading through the immediately precaution during disaster established by DDMA. State government had apply a resource person for each village leader and responsible for the spreading of immediately

warning during the flood situation.

Department Of Water Resource and Brahmaputra Board

The Central Government of India had apply National water policy and after the announcement the flood control activities had mainly started in Assam. In Assam for the rural areas the department of water resource had taken many initiatives till date and to protect the major township in Barak and Brahmaputra valley. The water resource department had not implemented long-term measures. However, the water resource department had only implemented for short term measures to control the flood disaster. Under the Ministry Of Water Resource the central Govt. had implemented Brahmaputra Board under Brahmaputra act in 1980. Department of water Resource had the responsibility to take the survey in both the areas in Brahmaputra and Barak valley and they need to take prevention to control the flood before the incident of flood disaster, and they also need to control the drainage system and bank erosion to control the floods. The Brahmaputra Board had also prepared plans to utilize the Water resource in Brahmaputra for hydropower, irrigation and other activities

Initiative steps of Government and NGOs

During Flood in Assam the Government and NGOs had taken measures initiatives to rescue the people from flood. In Assam when the flood incident happen (NDRF,SDRF) and Army had taken immediate action during the flood to rescue the people and other activities. To the flood victims the Central Government and State Government provide the basic commodities and facilities of hospital to the victims for the flood. However, during the Flood the NGOs also provide the essentials to the victims during the Flood.

Causes of Flood

The flood causes in assam is occur due to the heavy rainfall during the monsoon season and annual rainfall reach in Brahmaputra is 2480 mm and in northeastern hills is 6350 mm of rainfall, and in every year the Assam state were largely affected by flood. In assam the flood is also occur due to the seismicity and landslide, the Brahmaputra valleys falls under Zone V and it means highly risk of flood and the Brahmaputra valleys is

subjected to frequent tectonic activity zone. Moreover, In Assam the geographical areas also had problems for the occurs of natural disaster because the areas is surrounded by hilly areas, and rainfall also is very high and in the hilly areas the snow melted and directly flows to the downstream river due to the river water is increased the embankments of the rivers is breaking down.

The causes of Assam flood is also occur due to the man made caused like deforestation. The continuing deforestation in Assam is lead to heavy amount of top soil is coming down due to rains and in river, soils has followed during rains and the river water were collect lot of silt and sediments due to this the river water level is raised. The factors which cause flood in Assam are the bank erosion, earthquake activity and the high growth of population especially in the flood prone belt. The flood is also occur due to the no proper drainage system and the railway, buildings, roads and bridges, had restricted natural flows of water, in vulnerable areas the embankments is breaking down due to forced. However, another main reason is encroachment in forest lands and water bodies and that causes the flood in Assam. The other reason is caused the flood in Assam is man made reasons were the releasing of water from the dams. The unregulated release of water floods in Assam plains and in every year thousands of people of homeless due to the flood disaster in Assam.

Consequences of Flood

The Assam flood caused huge damage and loss of live and property, Highway roads, and the agricultural sector etc. In the recent flood of Assam in 2020 since May 22 according to the Assam state disaster management authority report 109 people had lost their life related by the flood incident and 56, 89,584 people had been affected by flood. However the state government had setup the relief came almost 621 reliefs came for the affected people.

1. In Assam the impact of agriculture sector is affecting the Assam economy. Due to the flood in Assam in every year the huge amount of agriculture sector is affected with the different seasonal and non-seasonal crops. In the flood of July 2016, according to the Assam tribune report

the total crop were damaged almost 99, 416, 44 hectares. In the rural areas of Assam the supplementary source of income are the livestock due to the recent flood were loss and affected from the various diseases and also death due to flood.

2. The socio-economic impact of roads and communication in Assam, most of the highway roads are affected due to flood like metaled and non-metaled roads and bridges due to water logging and flooding is effect communication problem. Natural disaster of flood is also caused rescue operations and disruption in relief. In the year 2011 due to flood the NH15 in Lakhimpur district, the Ronganadi bridge were affected and its create the communication problems for Lakhimpur and Dhemaji district and the other region for few hours had communication due to the caused natural disaster of flood in Assam.
3. In Assam the impact of employment and labour its lead to poverty due to the flood disaster. The agriculture sector is the main source occupation in rural areas, due to the flood they can't work in the agriculture for few months and it create unemployment. The agricultural lands and crops were destructed due to the flood disaster, and it affected in rural areas farmers, and farmers suffer from indebttness and the, were create the unemployment in the state of economy and it lead difficult of capital information in hazard affected areas by flood. Because due to less production capital can't forms. However, due to the farmer indebttness its does not make capital information and it create lack of funds and also it's create lack of income.
4. The socio-economic impact of forest resource, wildlife and the development activities in Assam. In the world Assam is the richest biodiversity zone and including various forests and wildlife sanctuaries. During the flood in Assam every year mostly animal were affected and killed by the flood disaster, due to the worst situation some animals like deer were moved away by flood in flowing river Brahmaputra and the forest resource also

destructive. The Assam state is biodiversity zone for swamp deer, elephant, horn rhino etc. The Impact In infrastructure and other development activities is highly cost to recovery and relief after the flood disaster. However, the government and private parties were discouraging the long-term investment in the recurrent flooding region. Due to the flood in every year the resources is loss and it create high costs of government to provide development schemes and services.

Conclusion

The Flood disaster in Assam was we analyze by collecting the data through newspaper, journal, internet and articles etc. During the flood hazard in Assam its effect socio-economic disturbance in every year after analyzing all the data and the major affected during the flood in rural areas and who lived near Brahmaputra and Barak Valley are also affected. The Flood in Assam is Occur in every year due to heavy rainfall and bank erosion and due to the flood is destructive the people livelihood, crop and infrastructure. In this research paper after analyzing about the flood mostly people in rural areas dependent in agriculture sector due to the flood had loss their economy and also for the overall development in the state had also critical problems in the economy. In Assam the flood is occur every year during the monsoon season and the central government and state government for the flood control and mitigation they did not taken properly for the long-term measures. However, the

central and state government should be taken proper action against the flood in Assam for the future generations and if they did not take sincerely it will Affected by the flood again in near future and proper steps should be taken by the concerned authorities to mitigate the same.

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